

Transforming education through inclusive school governance: Promoting collaboration between communities and classrooms

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ABSTRACT

Transforming education through inclusive school governance is essential for creating equitable, effective, and sustainable educational systems that meet the diverse needs of learners, educators, and communities. Inclusive governance encourages the active involvement of all stakeholders: principals, teachers, learners, School Governing Body (SGB) and parents in decision-making processes. This collaborative model promotes a sense of ownership, accountability, and shared responsibility, resulting in improved educational outcomes, enhanced learner performance, greater teacher engagement, and stronger community connections. However, implementing inclusive governance faces challenges such as resistance to change, resource limitations, and the need for ongoing professional development. Addressing these challenges requires the development of effective policies and frameworks informed by local and international best practices. Qualitative data were collected from principals, teachers, learners, and parents at four secondary schools through focus group and individual face-to-face interviews. The findings highlight that inclusive governance fosters a sense of belonging and empowerment, while also underscoring the need for continuous training and resource allocation. Recommendations include strengthening community partnerships, providing leadership opportunities for educators, and leveraging technology to enhance transparency and accessibility in governance processes. Case studies from schools successfully implementing inclusive governance models offer valuable insights into overcoming obstacles and achieving positive educational outcomes. Ultimately, the future of education hinges on a collective commitment to inclusive governance, promoting collaboration between communities and classrooms to ensure that every child thrives in a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

Keywords: collaboration, education, governance, inclusion, professional development

1 INTRODUCTION

Transforming education through inclusive school governance is a pivotal approach for addressing the diverse needs of learners, educators, and communities. Inclusive governance recognizes that school's function within a broader societal context, where collaboration between schools and communities is essential to ensure that education is equitable, effective, and responsive to all learners [1]. The active involvement of various stakeholders such as principals, teachers, parents, and learners in decision-making processes enables schools to reflect the values and priorities of the community. This shared responsibility fosters a sense of ownership and accountability that can significantly enhance educational outcomes and build stronger school-community relationships. As [2] emphasize, "Effective school governance is rooted in collaborative efforts, where all stakeholders work together to improve learning conditions and outcomes. The role of inclusive governance extends beyond administrative tasks; it involves developing a culture where the perspectives and needs of all members of the school community are considered. Schools that embrace inclusive governance can better support learners from marginalized backgrounds, empowering them with the resources and opportunities they need to succeed academically and socially. In this context, communities become essential partners, helping to bridge gaps and create a more supportive learning environment.

Implementing inclusive governance, despite its potential benefits, faces significant challenges such as resistance to change, resource limitations, and the ongoing need for professional development among educators. [3] emphasize that "overcoming these barriers requires the development of policies and strategies that promote equity and transparency." Effective leadership plays a pivotal role in fostering collaboration and inclusivity within schools. [4] notes that school leaders must create participatory governance structures where every voice, particularly those from historically marginalized communities, is heard and valued. The benefits of inclusive governance extend beyond improved learner performance to cultivating a cohesive and supportive school culture. [2] highlight that "when schools engage with their communities, they build a system of shared responsibility that enhances educational outcomes and social cohesion." Additionally, [5] point out that case studies of schools successfully implementing inclusive governance provide valuable insights into how these models can lead to improved academic achievement and community engagement. As [6] contend, "the future of education relies on restoring collaboration between classrooms and communities, creating inclusive, equitable learning environments where all learners can

thrive.” These findings underscore the transformative potential of inclusive governance in shaping education systems for the better.

The aim of this study is to investigate the factors contributing to the lack of inclusive school governance and its effects on restoring collaboration between communities and classrooms. As [7] emphasize, this analysis will provide “deeper insights into the issue” and support the development of “actionable recommendations to assist educational authorities and stakeholders in addressing governance challenges.” The growing absence of inclusive practices in school governance has raised concerns due to its “significant implications for educational outcomes and stakeholder relationships.” To tackle this critical issue, authorities must prioritize the adoption of comprehensive governance policies that are both collaborative and inclusive. According to [7] addressing the problem requires incorporating diverse perspectives and taking a broader, more inclusive approach” to governance reform.

1.1 Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to explore how inclusive school governance can transform education by fostering collaboration between communities and classrooms. By examining the strategies, perceptions, and challenges associated with inclusive governance, the study seeks to highlight its role in bridging the gap between schools and their surrounding communities. Inclusive school governance emphasizes the active involvement of stakeholders—such as parents, teachers, learners, and community members—in decision-making processes, which can enhance trust, accountability, and shared responsibility in addressing educational challenges. The research aims to provide actionable insights into how inclusive governance practices can promote equity, improve communication, and create a cohesive environment where all stakeholders contribute to the success of educational initiatives, ultimately transforming the way schools function within their communities.

1.2 Research question

How does inclusive school governance promote collaboration between schools and their surrounding communities to enhance educational outcomes and stakeholder engagement?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Concept and Principles of Inclusive School Governance

Inclusive school governance is a transformative approach founded on the principles of equity, transparency, and participatory decision-making. As [8] explain, it “ensures that all stakeholders learners, teachers, parents, and community members—contribute to the formulation and implementation of educational policies.” This approach prioritizes equitable access to decision-making processes, ensuring that marginalized voices are heard. [10] underscore that inclusive governance aligns with democratic education principles, advocating for shared accountability and collaborative problem-solving in schools. Equity is the cornerstone of this framework, requiring stakeholders to address systemic barriers that perpetuate disparities in educational opportunities. Transparency, another foundational principle, restores trust by ensuring that “decision-making processes are open and accessible” [11] Clear communication channels are essential for meaningful stakeholder participation. Participation emphasizes collective ownership and shared responsibility, with [10] highlighting how inclusive governance creates a “responsive school environment capable of adapting to socio-cultural and economic complexities.” These principles work in unison to build school systems that are equitable, transparent, and participatory, fostering collaboration and resilience.

2.2 Stakeholder Participation in School Governance

The active participation of stakeholders is central to inclusive school governance, fostering a collaborative ecosystem that strengthens accountability and educational equity. Parents, as primary caregivers, offer invaluable insights into their children’s needs. [12] emphasizes that “engaging parents in governance processes strengthens accountability and enhances educational outcomes.” Teachers contribute professional expertise, crucial for developing effective pedagogical strategies. [13] assert that when teachers are involved in governance, they are more motivated to implement innovative teaching practices and contribute to school improvement. Learners, as the primary beneficiaries of education, bring unique perspectives that ensure policies are grounded in their lived experiences. [14] note that “engaging learners in governance fosters leadership skills and a sense of agency, enabling them to become active participants in their education.” Community members, including local leaders and organizations, serve as advocates and resource mobilizers. According to [15], they bridge cultural and socio-economic gaps, ensuring that school policies are inclusive and contextually

relevant. Together, these stakeholders create a governance ecosystem that enhances collaboration and promotes inclusive, equitable educational practices.

2.3 Impact of Inclusive Governance on Educational Outcomes

Inclusive school governance has a direct and measurable impact on educational outcomes. Schools that implement inclusive governance often report higher learner achievement levels. According to [16], inclusive governance builds a supportive environment that nurtures academic excellence and learner well-being. Teacher engagement, driven by inclusive practices, results in improved instructional quality and professional satisfaction. Shatzer et al. (2014) found that teachers who participate in decision-making processes are more committed to their roles, leading to better classroom outcomes [17]. Beyond academic performance, inclusive governance fosters stronger school-community relationships. It builds trust and promotes a culture of collaboration, essential for addressing challenges such as absenteeism and dropout rates. Research also shows that schools with inclusive governance models experience fewer disciplinary issues, as stakeholders collectively work to create supportive environments [18]. This holistic impact underscores the transformative potential of inclusive governance in creating resilient and adaptive educational systems.

2.4 The Role of Leadership in Restoring Inclusive Governance

Leadership is a critical driver of inclusive school governance, with transformational leadership playing a pivotal role in restoring collaboration and empowering stakeholders. [19] argue that “effective leaders inspire collective action and ensure that all voices are represented in governance processes.” Transformational leaders are focused on building trust, restoring open communication, and promoting a shared vision among stakeholders. [20] supports this, emphasizing that such leadership fosters a cooperative environment by inspiring a common goal. Furthermore, leadership is key to overcoming systemic barriers in inclusive governance. [21] highlights that “leadership training is essential for school administrators to navigate the complexities of inclusive governance.” This training equips leaders with the skills necessary to manage diverse perspectives and implement policies that promote transparency, equity, and accountability.

2.5 Barriers to Implementing Inclusive School Governance

The implementation of inclusive school governance, while promising, encounters significant challenges that must be carefully addressed to realize its transformative potential.

One of the most pressing barriers is resource constraints, particularly in underfunded schools. According to [22], “schools in low-resource settings often lack the infrastructure and capacity to support inclusive governance models.” These resource limitations hinder the ability of schools to provide the necessary tools, training, and facilities required for effective governance practices. Without sufficient financial and material support, schools struggle to engage stakeholders meaningfully or foster collaborative decision-making. Another critical challenge is resistance to change among stakeholders, which can undermine efforts to implement inclusive practices. This resistance often stems from a lack of awareness or fear of losing control over decision-making processes. As [23] explains, “resistance is often rooted in a lack of awareness or fear of losing control over decision-making processes.” Such resistance highlights the importance of building trust and fostering open communication among all stakeholders to create an environment conducive to inclusive governance. Inadequate professional development further complicates the implementation of inclusive governance. Educators and leaders frequently lack the training and skills needed to adopt and sustain these governance practices. As [24] emphasizes, “capacity-building initiatives are essential to overcome these challenges.” Investing in sustained professional development programs is therefore vital, as they equip stakeholders with the competencies needed to navigate the complexities of inclusive governance. This comprehensive analysis of the challenges associated with implementing inclusive governance, such as resource constraints, resistance to change, and inadequate professional development, reflects the study's balanced and thoughtful approach. By addressing these barriers, the research not only acknowledges potential pitfalls but also underscores the critical steps needed to advance inclusive school governance effectively. Recognizing and overcoming these obstacles is essential to unlocking the full potential of collaborative governance in schools.

2.6 Best Practices and Policy Recommendations for Inclusive Governance

Implementing inclusive governance necessitates adopting evidence-based best practices that prioritize stakeholder engagement and foster collaboration. A critical step is the establishment of clear communication channels and participatory structures to ensure that all voices are represented and valued in decision-making processes. According to [25], “schools with dedicated governance committees, including representatives from all stakeholder groups, are more successful in restoring collaboration.” These committees create a platform for dialogue

and collective problem-solving, strengthening the sense of shared responsibility among stakeholders. Leveraging technology emerges as another pivotal strategy in enhancing transparency and accessibility within governance processes. The use of digital platforms facilitates communication, ensures timely updates, and broadens participation, particularly for stakeholders who may face barriers to in-person engagement. These technological advancements encourage more equitable and efficient governance practices, aligning with modern educational reform trends. Policy frameworks play an essential role in sustaining inclusive governance by embedding its principles within broader educational policies. [26] recommend “integrating inclusive governance into national education policies to ensure systemic adoption.” Such integration ensures that inclusive practices are not limited to isolated initiatives but are part of a cohesive and sustainable strategy across the education system. The use of case studies from successful models, such as community-led school improvement initiatives, provides actionable insights for overcoming challenges and implementing effective governance systems. These examples highlight how collaboration and local involvement can address context-specific issues, serving as a blueprint for other schools. By adopting these strategies, schools can create governance systems that are inclusive, resilient, and responsive to the needs of their communities. Addressing the barriers to implementation, as highlighted earlier, aligns with current trends in education reform and underscores the importance of adopting timely and practical solutions.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

A qualitative research approach was adopted for this study to explore the factors influencing inclusive school governance and its role in restoring collaboration between communities and classrooms. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of the phenomenon in its natural context. As noted by [27], qualitative research involves interpreting material practices to make complex social realities visible, making it well-suited for examining the lived experiences of principals, teachers, learners, and parents in relation to school governance practices and their impact on educational collaboration. The study emphasizes understanding the subjective realities of participants, as qualitative research focuses on exploring phenomena in depth [28]. This methodology is particularly effective for uncovering nuanced insights into how inclusive governance functions and influences stakeholder engagement. Semi-structured interviews were employed as the primary data collection method, providing flexibility while maintaining focus on participants' perceptions and experiences [29]. This

approach enabled the researcher to capture rich, detailed data that reflects the complexities of inclusive governance in secondary school contexts.

3.1 Data collection

The data collection process for this study utilized semi-structured focus group interviews and individual face-to-face interviews to explore the role of inclusive school governance in fostering collaboration between communities and classrooms. The focus group interviews included four principals, six teachers, six school governing body (SGB) members, six parents, and six learners from four secondary schools. The four secondary schools included in the study were selected based on specific criteria to ensure a diverse and representative sample. The selection considered geographic representation, with schools chosen from urban, semi-urban, and rural areas to reflect varied community dynamics. Schools with differing socioeconomic contexts were included to explore how governance practices are influenced by resource availability. Additionally, schools with diverse academic performance records were chosen to investigate potential correlations between governance and academic outcomes. Finally, willingness to participate and the availability of key stakeholders were essential considerations.

Semi-structured interviews were chosen for their flexibility, which enabled participants to share their ideas, perceptions, and views in depth. This approach aligns with the perspective of [30], who emphasize that such interviews offer "the space for participants to articulate their perspectives in detail." In addition to the focus group discussions, individual interviews were conducted with each principal to gain a deeper understanding of their unique perspectives on inclusive governance. As noted by [31], individual interviews "provide a platform for participants to tell their stories and reflect their reality," making them invaluable for capturing personal experiences and insights. These combined approaches ensured a comprehensive exploration of the participants' perceptions and experiences. Purposeful sampling was employed to select participants who could provide rich, relevant, and diverse information. The inclusion criteria were carefully defined: teachers were required to have a minimum of five years of experience, parents needed to have children enrolled at the selected schools, SGB members had to actively serve on the governance body, learners were required to be aged 12 to 17 and part of the learner representative council (LRC), and principals were included if they had at least four years of experience in their current roles. These criteria were designed to ensure that the participants represented a broad range of perspectives and

experiences related to inclusive school governance. The diversity of participants further enriched the study. Principals from each school provided leadership insights, while teachers from various subject areas and grades shared diverse pedagogical experiences. SGB members representing different governance roles contributed their perspectives on decision-making processes. Parents from varied socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds offered their views on collaboration, and learners, spanning different grades, genders, and leadership roles, shared their experiences of governance and its impact on the school community. Together, these methodological choices ensured a robust and comprehensive understanding of inclusive school governance and its role in fostering collaboration within the school community.

3.2 Data analysis

Data analysis for this study employed a thematic approach to examine the semi-structured focus group and individual interviews, with the aim of exploring how inclusive school governance fosters collaboration between communities and classrooms. The interviews were transcribed verbatim, and the data were analysed through a systematic coding process to identify recurring themes and patterns. This allowed for an in-depth understanding of participants' perceptions, experiences, and challenges surrounding inclusive governance. The thematic analysis followed the framework established by [31], which involves identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns or themes within qualitative data. The analysis involved an iterative process of reviewing interview transcripts, coding, categorizing, and identifying key themes that emerged from the data. This approach was guided by the research questions, particularly focusing on the strategies, challenges, and perceptions of various stakeholders on the role of inclusive governance in promoting school-community collaboration.

NVivo software was used to facilitate the organization and coding of the data, providing a structured approach to identifying key themes. This software supported a more systematic analysis by organizing the data into categories that were easier to manage and interpret. Triangulation of the data was conducted by comparing responses from the focus groups and individual interviews, ensuring that the identified themes were both reliable and valid. To enhance the trustworthiness of the analysis, member checking was conducted. This involved sharing the preliminary findings with a subset of participants to verify the accuracy of the interpretations and themes. Member checking aligns with the qualitative research principle of ensuring that participants' subjective experiences are captured accurately [30]. The final analysis provided rich insights into the role of inclusive governance in secondary schools and

its contribution to collaboration between schools and their surrounding communities, providing a deeper understanding of the transformative potential of inclusive school governance.

4. RESULTS

Six themes were identified from the information collected from the participants on the topic

Theme 1: Communication Among Stakeholders

The quality of communication within stakeholder groups is pivotal in determining the success of collaboration in educational settings. As [32] state, "the quality of communication within these groups significantly shapes the outcomes of collaboration." Similarly, [31] emphasizes that "the root causes of poor collaboration and stakeholder disengagement in schools often stem from ineffective communication channels," further supporting the critical role of clear and effective communication in fostering meaningful collaboration.

A principal of school C pointed out that: "*The communication gaps between teachers and parents are one of the biggest challenges we face. When parents feel left out of important decisions, they lose trust in the school's intentions. We try to involve them in meetings, but the message doesn't always get through clearly, and that leads to confusion and dissatisfaction. This breakdown in communication eventually trickles down to the learners, affecting their experience and participation in school activities.*"

A teacher' from school A added that: "*As a teacher, I often feel like I am caught in the middle. On one hand, I am expected to communicate with parents about their children's progress, but there's no structured channel for this communication. When misunderstandings arise, it feels like both sides blame us. It's frustrating because this lack of shared decision-making makes it harder for us to work collaboratively with parents for the benefit of the learners.*"

A parent's Perspective from school D said that: "*I often feel like our opinions as parents are not taken seriously. We are only informed about decisions after they've been made, not involved in the process. This creates misunderstandings, especially when we don't fully understand why certain policies or changes are implemented. Effective communication is essential if we are to truly support our children and the school.*"

Theme 2: Empowerment of Stakeholders

The active involvement of diverse groups in school governance created a sense of ownership and empowerment, particularly for teachers and parents who felt their contributions directly impacted school policies and outcomes [33].

Teacher from school D gave her opinion that: *"Participating in school governance has made me feel like I'm more than just an educator. Being able to voice my concerns about curriculum implementation and having those concerns addressed in policy decisions is empowering. It helps me connect with my role on a deeper level and shows that my input is valued."*

Parent from school C stated that: *"For the first time, I feel like a real partner in my child's education. Sitting in on meetings and discussing policies has shown me how much our voices can impact decisions. It's fulfilling to know that my suggestions, like changes to school schedules, have led to better outcomes for the children."*

An SGB Member's Perspective: *"Inclusive governance has been a game-changer for our school. Bringing together teachers, parents, and even learners ensures that every decision reflects the needs of the entire community. As an SGB member, I've seen how this approach strengthens our policies and creates a shared sense of purpose among all stakeholders."*

Learner from school A argued that:

"It's empowering to know that as learners, we have a platform to share our ideas and concerns. When our input is taken seriously, it motivates us to take our roles in governance seriously. It makes us feel like contributors to the school's success, not just passive participants."

Theme 3: Community-School Relationships

Inclusive governance has played a crucial role in bridging the gaps between schools and their surrounding communities, fostering trust and collaboration. As [34] notes, inclusive governance "enhances trust and collaboration in addressing school challenges and celebrating achievements

A principal from school D maintained that: *"Inclusive governance has transformed how we interact with the community. When parents and local leaders are involved in decision-*

making, there's a mutual sense of trust. It's no longer just about the school; it's about a shared vision for education, and that has strengthened our ability to address challenges."

A teacher of School B commented that: *"I've noticed a significant change in how the community supports our school since we started involving them more actively. Whether it's tackling disciplinary issues or celebrating learner achievements, the collaboration makes us feel like we're all on the same team working toward common goals."*

A parent from school A stated that: *"Before being included in governance, we felt disconnected from the school. Now, as we are part of the decision-making process, I see a stronger relationship between families and the school. It's easier to solve problems and celebrate milestones when we work together."*

An SGB member confirmed that: *"Bringing community voices into governance has bridged longstanding gaps. It's no longer about what the school can do alone but how the community and school can support each other. This trust has led to greater collaboration, from fundraising initiatives to addressing educational challenges."*

Learner Representative from school reported that: *"As learners, we feel a stronger connection to the community through inclusive governance. It's inspiring to see how our achievements are celebrated by everyone, and when issues arise, there's a collective effort to find solutions. It makes our education feel like a shared success story."*

Theme 4: Enhanced Learner Engagement

Learners involved in governance processes felt valued and respected, which improved their sense of belonging and commitment to school initiatives [35].

A teacher from school B concurred: *"Since learners have been actively involved in governance discussions, their engagement in class activities has improved significantly. They feel more connected to the school's objectives and policies, which reflects in their enthusiasm and participation."*

A parent from School B explained that: *"When learners are given a platform to voice their opinions in governance, they feel respected and valued. My child now shows a deeper interest in school projects and takes pride in contributing to the school's decisions."*

A principal from school A explained that: *"Enhanced learner engagement is one of the most noticeable outcomes of inclusive governance. Learners who participate in governance feel more accountable and motivated to perform well, both academically and in extracurricular activities."*

A Learner Representative from school C stated that: *"Being involved in governance has helped me understand how the school functions. It has also motivated me to encourage my peers to be more proactive in their learning and school activities because our voices are genuinely heard."*

An SGB members from school A: *"Learner engagement has significantly improved because they see themselves as part of the school's development. Their participation in governance activities has instilled a sense of responsibility and ownership over their education."*

Theme 5: Leadership Transformation

Principals and teachers recognized the transformative role of leadership in promoting inclusivity, emphasizing the importance of adopting a participatory and adaptive leadership style [36].

A principal from school B highlighted that *"Adopting a participatory leadership style has been a game-changer. When learners see leaders valuing their contributions, it motivates them to engage more actively in both academic and governance-related activities. Inclusivity starts with leadership, and it cascades into learner behaviour and participation."*

A Teacher from school D affirmed that: *"I've observed that when leadership is adaptive and open to collaboration, it directly impacts learner involvement. For instance, our inclusive policies, shaped by strong leadership, have encouraged learners to take on leadership roles themselves, fostering a culture of active participation."*

A learner Representative from school B alluded that: *"Our principal and teachers make us feel like partners in decision-making. This inclusive leadership makes us more committed to school activities because we know our input can make a difference. It's inspiring and boosts our confidence."*

A Parent from school C mentioned that *"Effective leadership that values inclusivity creates an environment where learners feel they belong. I've seen my child become more engaged*

because of the school's leadership approach, which prioritizes listening to learners and involving them in meaningful ways."

An SGB member from school A confirmed that *"Transformative leadership ensures that all stakeholders, including learners, are given a voice. This not only empowers learners but also enhances their engagement as they see that their opinions influence decisions. It's a powerful dynamic."*

Theme 6: Challenges and Barriers to Inclusivity

Key challenges included resistance to change, inadequate stakeholder training, and limited resources, which sometimes hindered effective implementation of inclusive governance practices [37].

A principal from school A illustrated that: *"One of the major barriers we face is resistance to change from some stakeholders. Many parents and even teachers are accustomed to traditional hierarchical models, making it challenging to introduce inclusive practices."*

A teacher from school C confirmed that: *"Resource constraints are a significant issue. While we support inclusivity in theory, the lack of training, time, and financial resources often limits how effectively we can implement these practices in governance."*

A parent school C stated that: *"Communication gaps between the school and parents hinder our involvement. Sometimes, we are unaware of governance meetings or decisions until it's too late, which makes it difficult to contribute meaningfully."*

A Learner Representative from school C supported that: *"Learners often feel underestimated in governance. While we are given a platform, our ideas are sometimes dismissed, which discourages active participation and reinforces a sense of exclusion."*

An SGB member from school D stressed that: *"Differing priorities among stakeholders often lead to misunderstandings. While we all want the best for the school, aligning our approaches is challenging due to diverse interests and expectations."*

5. DISCUSSION

The findings highlight the indispensable role of effective communication in fostering collaboration among educational stakeholders. [31] underscore how communication quality is a determinant of successful engagement, while its deficits often result in mistrust and

disengagement. The systemic consequences of poor communication, noting that gaps between teachers and parents erode trust, leading to dissatisfaction that ultimately impacts learners' experiences and participation. These dynamics illustrate how communication failures disrupt the synergy needed to create a cohesive and supportive educational environment.

The findings underscore the empowering impact of inclusive governance on diverse stakeholder groups, fostering a sense of ownership and meaningful contribution to school policies. Teachers should be valued when their professional insights, such as on curriculum implementation, are integrated into decision-making, deepening their connection to their roles. Parents also experience newfound empowerment through active participation, as illustrated by one parent who highlighted the tangible outcomes of their suggestions, such as improved school schedules. The transformative power of collaborative governance in uniting the community and aligning decisions with collective needs. The inclusion of learner voices further strengthens this dynamic, motivating learners to engage proactively and view themselves as integral to the school's success.

The findings highlight how inclusive governance fosters strong community-school relationships by bridging gaps and building trust among stakeholders. Involving parents and local leaders in decision-making creates a shared vision for education, enhancing the collective ability to address challenges. A teacher from School B echoed this sentiment, emphasizing how active community participation has cultivated a collaborative spirit, benefiting both disciplinary efforts and learner celebrations. Parents also feel more connected, as one parent shared that inclusion in governance has strengthened family-school relationships and streamlined problem-solving. Similarly, an SGB member highlighted that integrating community voices fosters trust and collaboration, enabling joint efforts like fundraising and tackling educational challenges. The transformative nature of this collaboration, with learners feeling empowered and supported through the shared celebration of achievements and collective problem-solving efforts.

The findings underscore the profound impact of inclusive governance on enhancing learner engagement, with learners feeling valued and respected through their active involvement. An improvement in learners' enthusiasm and class participation as they connected more deeply with the school's objectives and policies. When learners are given a voice in decision-making, they take pride in contributing and show greater interest in school initiatives.

Inclusive governance fosters a sense of accountability and motivation among learners, boosting their performance academically and in extracurricular activities. Learners' involvement instils a sense of responsibility, fostering ownership over their educational experiences and contributing to their holistic development.

The findings highlight the transformative power of inclusive leadership in fostering a participatory school culture that drives learner and stakeholder engagement. Participatory leadership motivates learners by valuing their contributions, creating a ripple effect on their academic and governance-related involvement. An adaptive leadership inspires learners to take on leadership roles themselves, cultivating a culture of active participation. Inclusive decision-making builds confidence and commitment to school activities. Leadership approaches emphasizing inclusivity create a sense of belonging among learners, boosting their engagement. Transformative leadership empowers all stakeholders, ensuring their voices influence decisions, thereby strengthening the collective ownership of the school's success

The findings reveal that challenges to implementing inclusive governance are multifaceted, often stemming from resistance to change, resource limitations, and misaligned stakeholder priorities. Challenges to inclusive governance are multifaceted, ranging from resistance to change and resource constraints to misaligned priorities among stakeholders. New emphasis is placed on communication gaps, which reduce meaningful participation, and learners' feelings of exclusion from governance processes. These barriers underscore the need for targeted interventions, such as capacity-building, improved communication strategies, and better alignment of stakeholder priorities. The inclusion of technology as a potential solution to bridge accessibility and transparency gaps

6. RECOMMENDATION

By adopting these recommendations, schools can advance inclusive governance, promoting stronger partnerships between communities and classrooms and creating a supportive environment for educational excellence.

6.1 Enhance Stakeholder Training

Schools should implement comprehensive training programs for all stakeholders, including principals, teachers, parents, and learner representatives, to build capacity in collaborative

governance. This training should cover communication skills, participatory leadership, conflict resolution, and decision-making processes to ensure effective and inclusive engagement. Strengthen

6.2 Communication Channels

Establish structured and reliable communication systems to facilitate regular updates, feedback, and transparency among stakeholders. Schools can adopt digital platforms and newsletters for timely dissemination of information, thereby bridging gaps and building trust.

6.3 Foster Resource Mobilization

Collaborate with government agencies, private organizations, and local community groups to secure funding and resources for implementing inclusive governance practices. These partnerships can address financial and infrastructural barriers, enabling sustainable and impactful initiatives.

6.4 Promote a Culture of Inclusivity

Encourage schools to adopt participatory leadership models that challenge traditional hierarchies. Stakeholders should be empowered to voice their opinions and contribute meaningfully to decision-making processes, fostering a shared sense of ownership and accountability.

6.5 Implement Monitoring and Evaluation Systems

Schools should establish mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of governance practices regularly. This could involve feedback from stakeholders, performance reviews, and audits of governance processes to identify and address challenges proactively.

6.6 Encourage Learner Leadership Development

Provide learners with opportunities to take on leadership roles within governance structures. This can be achieved through mentorship programs, learner council activities, and leadership workshops, which help develop their sense of responsibility and active participation.

6.7 Policies and Training Modules in Inclusive School Governance

The establishment of school-community liaison committees and annual participatory governance reviews to assess inclusivity. Training modules tailored for educators, school leaders, and governing body members could focus on building skills in conflict resolution,

facilitation of inclusive discussions, and leveraging digital tools for transparent communication. These modules could also incorporate culturally responsive practices, ensuring that diverse community voices are respected and valued in decision-making processes. Additionally, policies could emphasize regular capacity-building workshops and the development of governance toolkits, which include templates for drafting inclusive policies, best-practice case studies, and guidelines for conducting community consultations. By embedding these elements into the governance framework, schools would be equipped with both the knowledge and practical tools to foster meaningful collaboration between classrooms and communities, ultimately transforming education into a more inclusive and equitable system.

7. CONCLUSION

The study underscores the transformative potential of inclusive school governance in bridging the divide between communities and classrooms. By fostering collaborative decision-making, schools create a shared sense of responsibility and ownership among all stakeholders—teachers, parents, learners, and community members. This approach not only strengthens trust but also addresses educational challenges more effectively, as diverse perspectives are integrated into governance processes. Enhanced communication and the active participation of all stakeholders have been instrumental in building supportive relationships, enabling shared achievements and fostering a sense of unity in educational goals.

However, the study also reveals critical challenges, such as resistance to change, inadequate resources, and communication gaps, which hinder the full realization of inclusivity in governance. Addressing these barriers requires targeted strategies, including stakeholder training, resource allocation, and improved communication frameworks. Inclusive governance is not merely a structural adjustment but a cultural transformation that demands commitment from all participants. When implemented effectively, it holds the potential to not only improve educational outcomes but also strengthen the social fabric connecting schools to their communities. This integration paves the way for sustainable and impactful educational reform, ensuring equitable access and participation for all stakeholders.

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